

PULL-OUT TEST OF FRP BARS: THE EFFECT OF THE FREE END PROTRUDING PORTION OF THE BAR

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ABSTRACT

Concrete pull-out tests on glass fiber-reinforced polymer bar with a nominal diameter of 12 mm embedded in concrete were performed. The bonded length ranged from 5 to 20 times the nominal bar diameter. Specimens were tested with two free end conditions: with bar protruding from the bottom of concrete, and with bar cut flush with concrete. Results of pull-out tests were used to calibrate an interfacial cohesive material law (CML). The experimental results obtained indicate that protrusion at the free end significantly influenced the results. Different CMLs are obtained when results of specimens with different bonded lengths are used in the calibration process.

KEYWORDS

Pull-out-out Tests; FRP Bars; Protruding Part; Bond; GFRP Bars; Interfacial Cohesive Material Law

INTRODUCTION

Over the past decade, fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) bars have gained significant popularity in civil engineering applications. These bars are characterized by their anisotropic linear elastic nature, boasting impressive tensile strength and corrosion resistance (Fib, 2001; GangaRao et al., 2006; Zhao et al., 2022). FRP bars are manufactured using various types of fibers such as glass, carbon, aramid, and basalt, while different resins like polyester, vinyl ester, and epoxy are utilized to bind these fibers together. Moreover, a range of surface characteristics including sand coating, helical wrapping, indentation, and ribbing are employed (Solyom & Balázs, 2020). As a result, FRP bars with diverse fibers, geometries, and external surface features can be found in the market. The presence of such variability poses challenges in the design of FRP-reinforced concrete members, despite the existence of guidelines in the literature (ACI Committee 440.1R-15, 2015; CNR, 2007). A comprehensive understanding of the bond behavior between FRP bars and concrete becomes crucial, particularly considering the commercial availability and variability of FRP bars.

Numerous researchers have conducted studies on the bond behavior of FRP bars in concrete, exploring the influence of various parameters such as concrete cover (Afeiy et al., 2015; Veljkovic et al., 2017), bar diameter (Cosenza et al., 1997; Sayed Ahmad et al., 2011), concrete strength (Baena et al., 2009; Lee et al., 2008), environmental conditions (Khanfour & El Refai, 2017; Yan & Lin, 2017), and bonded length (Tighiouart et al., 1998). These investigations have employed different test methods, including concentric or eccentric direct pull-out tests (Baena et al., 2009, p. 2; Yan et al., 2016), as well as notched (Chai et al., 2021), continuous (Wambeke & Shield, 2006), and modified (Mazaheripour et al., 2013) beam tests to analyze the FRP-concrete bond behavior. Among these methods, concentric pull-out tests are widely favored due to their simplicity in execution and direct application of the pull-out force (Zhao et al., 2022). According to ASTM 7913 (ASTM D30, 2020), pull-out tests are typically conducted with a bonded length (ℓ) equal to five times the bar diameter (d_b). The pull-out test specimens might feature a protruding part of the FRP bar at the bottom of the cylinder (free end). The presence of this protrusion, alike other aforementioned parameters, can significantly affect the bond behavior. Furthermore, the impact of protrusion can vary depending on the surface characteristics of the FRP bars. However, conclusive investigations regarding the effects of protrusion on bond behavior have not been presented in the existing literature. To examine the influence of free end protrusion on the bond behavior between FRP and concrete, an experimental

campaign was conducted by the authors. The study focused on glass fiber-reinforced polymer (GFRP) bars, which are popular in the FRP bar market due to their affordability and accessibility. The pull-out tests were carried out under quasi-static loading conditions, following the guidelines of ASTM 7913 (ASTM D30, 2020). The GFRP bars utilized in the study were equipped with a ribbed surface to enhance bond strength. The nominal diameter (d_b) of the bar was 12 mm, however, the actual diameter provided by the manufacturer was 13.2 mm (Hudhayfah, 2021). Various bonded lengths (ℓ) were investigated, namely $5d_b$, $10d_b$, and $20d_b$. Two different surface treatments were considered for the GFRP bars: the first type had a coating to reduce the sharp edges resulting from the ribbing process, referred to as *lacquered*, while the second type remained *unlacquered*, i.e., without any coating. The pull-out specimens were divided in two sets: one with a protruding bar at the bottom of the concrete cylinder (free end), and another with the bar cut flush at the bottom of the cylinder. Linear variable displacement transformers (LVDTs) were employed to measure the displacement of both the free and loaded ends of the bar. The obtained results were analyzed to determine the effects of bar protrusion, the presence of the coating, and the bonded length.

EXPERIMENTAL CAMPAIGN

Materials

The pull-out test specimens and material characterization cylinders were cast using normal weight concrete from a single batch. The mix proportions consisted of water, cement, fine aggregate, and coarse aggregate in the ratio of 1:3.4:10.4:10.8, with a maximum aggregate size of 9.53 mm. A slump test, conducted according to ASTM C143 (ASTM C09, 2020b), provided a slump value of 191 mm during casting. After casting, plastic sheets were used to cover all specimens for 24 hours. Subsequently, the specimens were demolded and subjected to wet burlap curing. Moist curing was maintained for 28 days for all specimens. Compressive strength and splitting tensile strength were determined according to ASTM C39 (ASTM C09, 2020a) and ASTM 496 (ASTM C09, 2017), respectively. At 28 days, the average compressive strength from three specimens (f'_c) was 40.3 MPa, while the average splitting tensile strength (f'_t) was 3.1 MPa. The study used GFRP bars, featuring ribs as shown in Figure 1a. Two types of GFRP bars were utilized, distinguished by their surface treatment. The bar with a thin coating layer was designated as lacquered (L), while the bar without any coating was referred to as unlacquered (UL). Both bars had a nominal diameter (d_b) of 12 mm, with an actual diameter of 13.2 mm according to the manufacturer's datasheet (Hudhayfah, 2021). This diameter corresponded to a cross-sectional area (A_b) of 137 mm². The mechanical properties of L bars are: ultimate tensile strength 1096 MPa and Young's modulus 64.2 GPa. For the UL bars, the ultimate tensile strength is 1155 MPa and Young's modulus is 62.5 GPa.

Specimen preparation and pull-out test setup

A total of 33 pull-out specimens were prepared for the study, comprising 17 specimens utilizing GFRP bars with a lacquered surface, and 16 specimens employing GFRP bars without any surface coating (unlacquered). While following the guidelines of ASTM 7913 (ASTM D30, 2020), which recommend a bonded length equal $5d_b$, recent research has revealed that the bond behavior of GFRP bars is significantly influenced by the bonded length (ℓ) (Zhao et al., 2022). Consequently, the study included specimens with different bonded lengths. To accommodate the specific formwork requirements for specimens with varying bonded lengths, cylindrical concrete specimens were cast instead of the traditionally employed cube specimens as described in ASTM 7913 (ASTM D30, 2020). However, for the sake of comparison, five cubic specimens were prepared in accordance with the ASTM 7913 (ASTM D30, 2020) guidelines, featuring a bonded length of $5d_b$ (three with L bars and two with UL bars). Both L and UL GFRP bars were used to cast specimens with three different bonded lengths, i.e., $\ell = 5d_b$, $10d_b$, and $20d_b$, corresponding to bonded lengths of 60 mm, 120 mm, and 240 mm, respectively.

Cylindrical tubes, commonly utilized in the concrete construction industry, served as molds for casting the cylinders with embedded bars. A 3D printed plastic piece, featuring a central hole to accommodate the GFRP bar, was positioned atop each tube. Additionally, a plywood base, equipped with a centrally positioned hole, was securely affixed to the bottom end of each tube. This arrangement ensured precise alignment of the GFRP bar with the cylinder axis, resulting in a

protrusion of 50 mm at the bottom of each cylinder. In some specimens, the protruded section of the bar was subsequently cut off to be flush with the cylinder surface prior to testing.

Figure 1: Test setup, GFRP bars, molds, and microscopic images

To create a bond breaker between the GFRP bar and the surrounding concrete at the top of the specimen, a PVC pipe was tightly screwed into the top plastic piece, resulting in a 140 mm long unbonded area. The casting process involved vertically orienting the cylinders and pouring the concrete in three distinct layers from the top end for each specimen. A photo of the cylindrical tube and bar formwork prior to casting is provided in Figure 1b. For comprehensive details regarding the casting procedure, the reader can refer to (Zhao et al., 2022). The test set-up, based on the recommendation of ASTM D7913 (ASTM D30, 2020), involved restraining the concrete cylinder with an embedded GFRP bar between two steel plates. These plates, referred to as top and bottom plates, were connected by four steel rods. To measure the loaded end slip of the bar, referred to as g , three linear variable displacement transformers (LVDTs) were installed. To facilitate gripping of the bar by the jaws of the servo-hydraulic testing machine, a threaded hollow cylinder of length 305 mm, denoted as L_{cyl} , was used at the end of the bar. The detailed test set-up can be found in (Zhao et al., 2022). During the static pull-out tests, the average displacements measured by the top three LVDTs were used to control the test, with a test rate of 0.88 mm/min.

Results and discussions

The pull-out specimens were named using the following convention: X-Y-Z-N. X represents the type of bar used in the cylinder, either L for lacquered bars or UL for unlacquered bars. Y indicates the bonded length, with values of 5, 10, or 20 corresponding to $5d_b$, $10d_b$, and $20d_b$, respectively. Z provides information about the end condition of the specimens, with P indicating a protruded part of the bar and C indicating the protruding part of the bar was cut off. N denotes the specimen number. The inclusion of ASTM at the beginning of the specimen name signifies that the specimens were cast following the specimen geometry outlined in ASTM D7913 (ASTM D30, 2020). Table 1 provides detailed information on all the pull-out tests, including the specimen's name, bonded length (ℓ), failure mode, and peak load (P^*). Additionally, the table presents the coefficient of variation (CoV) for each group of specimens. Figure 2 illustrates the relationship between the applied load (P) and the loaded end slip (g) for all the pull-out tests conducted. Initially, the load response exhibits a linear behavior, which transitions into a non-linear segment before reaching the peak load (P^*).

Table 1: Pull-out test results for all the specimens

Specimen	ℓ (mm)	P^* (kN)	Failure mode	\bar{P}^* (kN) [CoV]	$\bar{\bar{P}}^*$ (kN) [Cov]
L-5-C-1	60	25.04	S		
L-5-C-2	60	17.99	S	21.75	
L-5-C-3	60	22.21	S	[0.133]	
UL-5-C-1	60	21.92	S		22.32
UL-5-C-2	60	21.83	S	22.90	[0.025]
UL-5-C-3	60	24.94	S	[0.063]	
L-5-P-1	60	53.60	S		
L-5-P-2	60	50.17	S	52.93	
L-5-P-3	60	54.74	S	[0.032]	
L-5-P-4	60	53.21	S		53.96
UL-5-P-1	60	53.70	S		[0.019]
UL-5-P-2	60	57.59	S	54.99	
UL-5-P-3	60	55.07	S	[0.029]	
UL-5-P-4	60	53.61	S		
L-10-C-1	120	64.60	S		
L-10-C-2	120	63.15	S	66.79	
L-10-C-3	120	72.62	S	[0.062]	
UL-10-C-1	120	57.48	S		63.94
UL-10-C-2	120	64.17	S	61.09	[0.045]
UL-10-C-3	120	61.62	S	[0.045]	
L-20-C-1	240	105.8	S	105.8	
UL-20-C-1	240	103.50	S	106	105.9
UL-20-C-2	240	108.5	S	[0.023]	[0.019]
L-20-P-1	240	137.50	R		
L-20-P-2	240	129.17	R	136.19	
L-20-P-3	240	141.90	R	[0.039]	
UL-20-P-1	240	136.10	R	138.70	137.44
UL-20-P-2	240	141.30	R	[0.019]	[0.009]
ASTM-L-5-P-1	60	50.64	S		
ASTM-L-5-P-2	60	48.45	S	52.45	
ASTM-L-5-P-3	60	58.25	S	[0.080]	
ASTM-UL-5-P-1	60	50.36	S	51.08	51.76
ASTM-UL-5-P-2	60	51.80	S	[0.014]	[0.013]

S=slippage of the bar with respect of concrete; R=tensile rupture of the bar; \bar{P}^* : average peak load of nominally equal specimens; $\bar{\bar{P}}^*$: average peak load of specimens with equal bonded length

Figure 2: Applied load versus loaded end slip for all pull-out tests

Following the peak load, the descending portion of the response is characterized by load oscillations as the slip (g) increases. These oscillations have been previously observed in a study conducted by the authors, involving a different type of GFRP bar with a sand-coated surface (Zhao et al., 2022). The

findings from this study, as well as previous research, suggest that these oscillations are influenced by the surface characteristics of the GFRP bar. During the pull-out tests, the predominant mode of failure observed in most specimens was the slippage of the bar relative to the concrete interface. However, in cases where a protrusion was present at the free end and the bonded length was $20d_b$, tension failure of the bars outside the bonded area was observed. The tests were terminated either upon significant slip or rupture of the GFRP bar. Subsequently, a concrete prism containing the embedded bar was carefully removed from the cylinder to preserve the integrity of the bar-concrete interface. Microscopic images were captured along the bonded area, specifically for specimen UL-5-P-1, as depicted in Figure 1d. These images revealed that the ribs on the bar surface were sheared off during the bar slippage, indicating that the strength of the concrete was sufficient to make the ribs of the bar the critical point of failure. Figure 1d further illustrates the absence of ribs on the bar surface at the end of the test. Notably, Figure 1d displays the accumulation of resin residue towards the free end of the specimens, which correlates with the shearing off of the ribs as the bar slipped with respect to the concrete. Figure 3a illustrates the effect of bar protrusion on specimens utilizing lacquered bars with bonded lengths of $5d_b$ and $20d_b$, including specimens following the recommended geometry of ASTM 7913 (ASTM D30, 2020). The observed responses suggest that the presence of a protruding part influences the peak load. Referring to Table 1, the average peak load \bar{P}^* for specimens with lacquered bars and a bonded length of $5d_b$, along with a protruded bar, was 52.93 kN, while \bar{P}^* for the cut-off specimens was 21.75 kN. Thus, the protruded part of the bar increased the peak load by 31 kN for specimens with $5d_b$ and lacquered bars. A similar increase in the peak load was also noted for specimens with a protruded part at the free end and a bonded length of $20d_b$.

Figure 3: Applied load versus loaded end slip

The load responses of specimens with lacquered (L) and unlacquered (UL) bars are compared in Figure 3b. These responses correspond to specimens where the protruding part of the bar was cut off. The findings suggest that the coating had a limited impact on the peak load. By referring to Table 1, it is observed that for certain lengths and free end conditions, the average peak load of L bar specimens surpasses that of UL specimens, while in other cases, the opposite trend is observed.

The bond strength (τ^* , i.e., average interfacial shear stress at peak load) in accordance with ASTM 7913 (ASTM D30, 2020) can be calculated using the formula:

$$\tau^* = \frac{P^*}{\pi d_b \ell} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

Figure 4a illustrates the relationship between τ^* and ℓ for the pull-out tests conducted in this study. It is observed that when a protruding part is present at the free end, the bond strength decreases as the

bonded length increases. However, for specimens with the bar cut off at the free end, both for L and UL bars, τ^* increases from $\ell = 5d_b$ to $\ell = 10d_b$ and then decreases from $\ell = 10d_b$ to $\ell = 20d_b$. Additionally, Figure 4a confirms that the surface treatment of the bar had minimal influence on the peak load.

Figure 4: Bond strength and stress over bonded length

Figure 4b presents the relationship between the average GFRP bar stress ($\bar{f}_b^* = 4\bar{P}^*/(\pi 13.2^2)$) at peak load and the bonded length (ℓ). ACI 440.1R-15 (ACI 440, 2015, p. 440) provides the relationship between the stress in the bar for structural applications (f_{fr}) and the development length (ℓ_d):

$$\ell_d = \frac{\alpha \frac{f_{fr}}{0.083\sqrt{f'_c}} - 340}{13.6 + \frac{C}{d_b}} d_b \quad (\text{S.I. units}) \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

where the bar location modification factor α was set equal to 1, and the spacing from the cover to the center of the GFRP bar, denoted as C , was chosen equal to the concrete cylinder radius, i.e., 101 mm. The plot in Figure 4b also includes the curve representing the relationship between f_{fr} and ℓ_d based on Eq. 2. In general, the graph shows that the bonded length required to achieve a certain bar stress (f_b^*) in the pull-out tests is smaller than the development length in structural applications to achieve the same value of f_{fr} . According to the pull-out tests (Table 1), a bonded length of $20d_b$ or 240 mm is necessary to reach bar failure when a protrusion is present, whereas Eq. 2 suggests that it could be more than 1000 mm to reach the bar failure.

CALIBRATION OF THE CML

Similar load responses were obtained from pull-out tests of L and UL bars, which implies that similar CMLs characterize the bar-concrete interface for these bars. At the current step of this research, only the experimental results of specimens with L bars are considered for the determination of the interfacial CML.

For each bonded length of specimens with L bar, an average relation between the global slip g and the applied force P was derived from the experimental data by averaging the pull-out forces P associated with any loaded end slip g (Figure 5). These average relations were referred to as average experimental P - g responses herein and were used to calibrate the bar-concrete interfacial cohesive material law (CML) using two alternative procedures. It should be noted that the average experimental P - g response for bar without protruding part and $\ell = 20d_b$ was determined based on the

results of one specimen, since the results of only one specimen were available in this case. For any bonded length ℓ , both procedures involve the analytical computation of the function $P_\ell(g)$, which associates the global slip g to the corresponding pull-out force P_ℓ when a CML depending on certain parameters (specified in the following section) collected in an array τ is defined. Functions $P_\ell(g)$ were called analytical load responses in this paper.

The first procedure consists in minimizing the distance between the analytical and the average experimental load responses corresponding to each bonded length adopted in the experiments. In particular, the parameters in the array τ were determined by minimizing the function:

$$f_1(\tau) = \sum_{j=1}^N (P_j^{\text{exp}} - P_\ell(g_j))^2 \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where g_j and P_j^{exp} are the loaded end slip and corresponding pull-out force of the P - g response considered, and N is the number of points considered in the mentioned response.

Figure 5: Experimental responses

As a result, a CML was determined for each bonded length and set of specimens (without or with protruding part of bar). These CMLs were denoted as $\text{CML}_{P_g}^\ell$, where ℓ is the bonded length of the specimens used in the calibration process expressed in millimeters and the subscript reminds that the CML was derived based on a P - g response. A unique CML for each set of specimens (with or without protruding part of bar) was then obtained by averaging the CMLs corresponding to different bonded lengths. The average CMLs were named CML_{P_g} . It should be noted that the superscript ℓ was dropped because they corresponded to the averages for all bonded lengths.

The second procedure consists in minimizing simultaneously the distance between the analytical and the average experimental responses corresponding to all the bonded lengths. In particular, the parameters in the array τ were determined by minimizing the function:

$$\bar{f}_1(\tau) = \sum_{k=1}^{N_\ell} \left[\frac{\sqrt{f_{1,k}(\tau)}}{P_{\max,k}} \right]^2 \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

where N_ℓ is the number of bonded length considered, $P_{\max,k}$ is the maximum experimental pull-out load corresponding to the k^{th} bonded length, and $f_{1,k}(\tau)$ is evaluated with Eq. 3 with the average experimental and analytical responses corresponding to the k^{th} bonded length ($k=1,2,3$ for specimens without protruding part of bar and $k=1,2$ for specimens with protruding part of bar). In this case, a unique CML was determined for each set of specimens. These CMLs were called global CMLs and denoted with CML_{P_g} .

CML and construction of the analytical load responses

A piecewise multilinear CML function was considered, which is defined by:

$$\tau(s) = \begin{cases} \tau_j + \frac{\tau_{j+1} - \tau_j}{s_{j+1} - s_j} (s - s_j) & \text{if } s_j \leq s < s_{j+1} \quad (j=1, \dots, n-1) \\ \tau_n & \text{if } s = s_n \\ 0 & \text{if } s > s_n \end{cases} \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

where τ is the bar-concrete interfacial shear stress at a certain point of the interface, where the interfacial slip s (bar-concrete relative displacement) occurs, $\mathbf{s} = [s_1, s_2, \dots, s_k, s_{k+1}, \dots, s_n]$ is an array of interfacial slips arranged in ascending order (with $s_1 = 0$), and $\boldsymbol{\tau} = [\tau_1, \tau_2, \dots, \tau_k, \tau_{k+1}, \dots, \tau_n]$ is the array collecting the interfacial shear stress corresponding to the slips in \mathbf{s} . When calibrating a CML based on a certain experimental P - g response (if the first procedure is used) or a certain set of P - g responses (if the second procedure is used) s_n was set equal to the maximum global slip of the average P - g response(s). The distance $\Delta s = s_{j+1} - s_j$ ($j=1, \dots, n-1$) between two consecutive slips in \mathbf{s} was constant but different for $j \leq k-1$ and $j \geq k$. In particular, Δs was smaller for $s \leq s_k$ than for $s > s_k$ to obtain a more refined evaluation of the first branch of the CML. s_k was chosen in the first portion of the descending branch of the P - g response(s) (after the peak load) and Δs was chosen in the range $[0.1, 0.3]$ mm for $j \leq k-1$ and in the range $[0.2, 0.7]$ mm for $j \geq k$.

The shear stress transfer (fracture mechanics Mode-II) at the bar-concrete interface in a pull-out test is governed by the following equation:

$$\frac{d^2}{dy^2} s(y) = \frac{\pi d_b}{E_b A_b} \tau(y) \quad \text{Eq. 6}$$

where y is a reference axis along the bar with the origin at the free end, and E_b and A_b are the elastic modulus and the cross-sectional area of the bar, respectively. Eq. 6 is valid under the assumptions: i) the interfacial shear stress τ at any location depends only on the slip s at the same location; ii) the bar behavior is linear elastic; iii) the longitudinal stress and strain are constant in the cross-section of the bar; iv) the displacements of the concrete are negligible with respect to the displacements of the bar (which implies that the slips coincide with the longitudinal displacements of the bar). By enforcing at the free end the boundary conditions:

$$s(0) = \delta \quad \varepsilon_b(0) = \left. \frac{ds}{dy} \right|_0 = 0 \quad \text{Eq. 7}$$

for increasing values of the free end slip δ , a slip profile $s(y)$ and a bar strain profile $\varepsilon_b(y)$ can be associated with any value of δ . A pull-out force $P_\ell = E_b A_b \varepsilon_b(\ell)$ and a global slip $g = s(\ell)$ are then associated with any value of δ . The $P_\ell(g)$ is finally obtained by plotting $P_\ell = E_b A_b \varepsilon_b(\ell)$ versus $g = s(\ell)$. If the relation between the shear stress and the slip is such that the free end slip δ is zero up to a finite value \tilde{P}_ℓ of the pull-out force, the initial branch of the $P_\ell(g)$ function (up to \tilde{P}_ℓ) can be determined by enforcing the boundary conditions in Eq. 7 with $\delta = 0$ at different distances ξ from the loaded end (i.e., the origin of the y -axis is placed at the distance ξ from the loaded end). A loaded end slip $g = s(\xi)$ and a pull-out force $P_\ell = E_b A_b \varepsilon_b(\xi)$ are then associated with any value of ξ in the range $[0, \ell]$ (Focacci & Carloni, 2015).

CMLs obtained and discussion

Figure 6a shows the CMLs obtained for specimens with and without protruding part of the bar using the first procedure. In this case, a CML was obtained for each bonded length and for each set of specimens with L bar (with and without protruding part, respectively). Figure 6b shows the average

CMLs, which were obtained by averaging the ordinates of the CMLs corresponding to different bonded lengths for the same set of specimens. The average CMLs were named CML_{Pg} .

Figure 6: CMLs obtained using the calibration procedure

It can be observed that different CMLs were obtained when experimental responses of specimens with different bonded lengths were introduced in the calibration process. Figure 7 reports the average experimental P - g responses of the specimens without protruding part of FRP bar for all bonded lengths. The corresponding analytical $P_\ell(g)$ functions, obtained by introducing in Eq. 6 the CML_{Pg}^ℓ with $\ell = 60$ mm (Figure 7a), $\ell = 120$ mm (Figure 7b), and $\ell = 240$ mm (Figure 7c) are plotted as well for comparison.

Figure 7: Average experimental P - g responses and $P_\ell(g)$ functions for bonded length equal to 60, 120, and 240 mm

The $P_\ell(g)$ functions shown in Figure 7 were labelled in such a way that it is possible to identify which CML was used to obtain them. A superscript X , i.e., $P_\ell^X(g)$, was added and referred to the bonded length ℓ used to calibrate the CML_{Pg}^ℓ . The subscript ℓ in $P_\ell^X(g)$ refers to the bonded length used to solve Eq. 6. For example, in Figure 7a the $P_{120}^{60}(g)$ curve was obtained by solving Eq. 6 in the range $[0, \ell = 120 \text{ mm}]$ and using the CML calibrated based on the specimens with $\ell = 60$ mm, i.e., CML_{Pg}^{60} . Each plot in Figure 7 includes a sub-plot where the three CML_{Pg}^ℓ determined for the bar without protruding part are shown and the one used in Eq. 6 to construct the analytical $P_\ell^X(g)$ in the plot is identified with a black line. It can be observed that each CML_{Pg}^ℓ allows to obtain an analytical $P_\ell^X(g)$ response overlapped to the average experimental P - g response for the same bonded length used to calibrate the CML itself, i.e., the analytical and experimental responses are very similar when $X = \ell$. On the other hand, the pull-out force of the $P_\ell^X(g)$ functions tend to overestimate or underestimate the pull-out force of the corresponding experimental responses for $X \neq \ell$. Interestingly

a clear trend can't be detected from the results in Figure 7: the CML_{Pg}^{60} allows to predict accurately the results of specimens with $\ell = 60$ mm, underestimates the pull-out forces of specimens with $\ell = 120$ mm and overestimates the pull-out forces of specimens with $\ell = 240$ mm. A similar observation applies for the CML_{Pg}^{120} and CML_{Pg}^{240} . Figure 8 shows the analytical $P_\ell(g)$ responses, labelled $P_\ell^{av}(g)$, obtained by introducing the CML_{Pg} (Figure 6b) in Eq. 6. $P_\ell^{av}(g)$ are compared in the same figure with the average experimental $P-g$ responses. Figure 8a and b refer to the specimens without and with the protruding part of the bar at the free end, respectively. Each plot includes a subplot, where the CML used to compute the corresponding $P_\ell(g)$ is reported with the same color.

Figure 8: Comparison of the functions $P_\ell(g)$ obtained with the CML_{Pg} and \overline{CML}_{Pg} , and the average experimental $P-g$ responses

It can be observed that for specimens without protruding part of bar the $P_\ell^{av}(g)$ functions constructed based on the average CML overestimate the corresponding experimental responses for the shorter embedment lengths and underestimate them for the longer embedment lengths. The opposite is true for specimens with protruding part of the bar.

The global CMLs, determined according to the second procedure by minimizing simultaneously the distance (Eq. 4) between the analytical and the experimental responses corresponding to all the bonded lengths (\overline{CML}_{Pg}), are shown and compared with the CMLs determined by averaging the CMLs associated with each bonded length (CML_{Pg}) in the sub-plot of Figure 8a (without protrusion) and Figure 8b (with protrusion). It can be observed that the two procedures produce similar results. The $P_\ell(g)$ functions obtained by introducing the global CML in Eq. 6, labelled $\overline{P}_\ell(g)$, are compared with the average experimental $P-g$ responses in Figure 8. It can be observed that the $\overline{P}_\ell(g)$ functions are similar to the $P_\ell^{av}(g)$ functions and are characterized by smaller pull-out forces at the same global slip.

From the calibration approaches described above, it can be argued that different bonded lengths have to be considered when assessing the shear stress transfer phenomenon at the bar-concrete interface. In fact, a CML that allows to capture the experimental results of specimens with a certain bonded length, not necessarily allows to capture the experimental results of specimens with a longer or shorter bonded length. In addition, a clear trend of the influence of the bonded length can't be detected for the bar considered in this work: a CML calibrated on the basis of experimental results with a certain bonded length not necessarily underestimates or overestimates experimental $P-g$ responses of specimens with longer or shorter embedment lengths.

For the bar considered in this work, a strong effect of the presence of the protruding part of bar at the free end of the specimens was observed. It can be argued that the protruded part of the bar produces a resistance to the slippage of the bar when is pulled inside the concrete block. This resistance needs to be added to the pull-out force applied to the loaded end. For this reason, the CMLs calibrated by neglecting this phenomenon based on specimens with a protruding part of bar at the free end does not represent the actual interfacial shear stress transfer.

CONCLUSIONS

Pull-out tests were conducted following ASTM 7913 (ASTM D30, 2020) to examine the influence of bar protrusion at the free end of the specimens. The study considered two surface treatments (lacquered and unlacquered) and three bonded lengths ($5d_b$, $10d_b$, and $20d_b$). The P - g responses exhibited typical behavior with post-peak oscillations, attributed to bar surface characteristics. Comparing specimens with lacquered bar, both with protruded and cut-off specimens, it was evident that protrusion at the free end significantly increased peak loads. The effect of surface coatings on peak loads was minimal. Two procedures were applied for the calibration of the bar-concrete interfacial CML of the bars with lacquered surface. The first procedure averages different CMLs, each one determined based the results of specimens with a certain bonded length, whereas the second procedure simultaneously considers the results of specimens with different bonded lengths. From the calibration analysis the following conclusions can be outlined for the bar considered in this work.

1. The two procedures provide similar results. Slightly better results in terms of capability of the obtained CML to capture the experimental results of specimens with different bonded lengths are provided by the second procedure.
2. Specimens with different bonded lengths must be considered when calibrating the interfacial CML, since a CML calibrated based on results of pull-out specimens with a certain bonded length not necessarily allows to capture the experimental results of specimens with longer or shorter embedment lengths.
3. Specimens without protruding part of bar must be considered when calibrating the interfacial CML, since the protruding part of bar has a strong effect on the pull-out response, which does not depend on the interfacial shear stress transfer along the bonded length.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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